

Excess Weight in the Italian Regions

He grew up in 1.1 between 2005 and 2020

The Istat-Bes calculates the value of excess weight in the Italian regions. Excess weight is defined as a standardized proportion of 18 -year -old people and more overweight or obese on the total of 18 -year -old people and more. The indicator refers to the classification of the World Healthcare Organization of the body mass index. The data refer to the period between 2005 and 2020.

Ranking of the Italian regions for the value of the excess weight in 2020. Campania is in the first place due to the value of excess weight with a value equal to 55.3 units, followed by Sicily with a value equal to 51.2 and the Basilicata with an amount equal to 50. In the middle of the standings there are Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an amount of 44.3 and Veneto and Umbria with a value of 43.9. Piedmont close the ranking with an amount equal to 41.9, followed by Trentino-Alto Adige with an amount of 40.7 and from Tuscany with an amount equal to 40.4.

Variation of excess weight between 2005 and 2020 in the Italian regions. The Aosta Valley is in the first place for growth of excess weight in percentage value between 2005 and 2020 with a value of 18.53% or equal to an amount of 6.8 units, followed by Lombardy with a value equal to 13.05% equal to an amount of 5 units and from Piedmont with a value of 8.27% equal to an amount of 3.2 units. In the middle of the standings there are Molise with an amount equal to 1.02% equal to an amount of 0.5 units, followed by Emilia Romagna with an amount of 0.67% or equal to an amount of 0.3 units, and from the Marche with a variation equal to an amount of -1.14% equal to an amount of -0.5 units. Trentino Alto -Adige close the ranking with a value equal to -6.44% equal to an amount of -2.8 units, followed by Abruzzo with a value equal to -8.64% equal to an amount of -4 , 4 units and from Puglia with a value equal to -9.43% equal to an amount of -5 units. On average, the value of the percentage variation of weight excess has grown an amount of 0.46% in the period between 2005 and 2020.

Italian macro-regions. The value of weight excess has grown in northern Italy while decreasing in other macro-regions or in central Italy and southern Italy. Overall, in Italy the value of excess weight has increased by a value of 1.11 units. Specifically in northern Italy the value of excess weight has grown from an amount of 40.90 units up to a value of 43.40 units or a growth of an amount of 2.50 units equal to an amount of 6.11 %. In Central Italy the value of excess weight has decreased from an amount of 43.90 units up to a value of 42.20 units or equal to an amount of -1.70 units equal to a value of -3.87%. In the South, the value of excess weight has decreased from an amount of 50.80 units up to a value of 50.40 units or equal to a variation of -0.40 units equal to an amount of -0.79%.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Specifically two different Clusters are identified or:

- *Cluster 1:* Puglia, Campania, Basilicata, Molise, Sicily, Calabria, Abruzzo;

¹ Ph.D., Assistant Professor of Economics at Lum University Giuseppe Degennaro, and researcher in Economics at LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Statale 100 km 18, Bari, Puglia, Italy. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it

- *Cluster 2*: Lombardy, Tuscany, Valle d'Aosta, Piedmont, Sardinia, Trentino-Alto Adige, Liguria, Veneto, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Lazio, Marche, Emilia-Romagna, Umbria.

Considering the value of the C1 median, an amount equal to 49.3 is obtained while the value of the C2 median is equal to an amount of 43.3 units. It follows that the algorithm system consists of $C1 > C2$. It therefore follows that the inhabitants of Southern Italy have a higher level of excess weight than that of the inhabitants of the North. The economic gap therefore also acquires a strictly health meaning.

Network Analysis. Through the use of Manhattan distances it is possible to create a Network Analysis to check if there are relationships between the various regions for the value of access to weight. The analysis shows the presence of three different network structures of which 2 are complex and 1 is instead simplified or biunivocal. There is a network structure between Piedmont, Lombardy and Valle d'Aosta with defined or:

- Piedmont has a link with Lombardy with a value equal to 1.0;
- Lombardy has a link with the Aosta Valley for a value of 0.95.

There is a complex network structure between Lazio, Veneto, Marche and Friuli-Venezia Giulia. Particularly:

- Lazio has a link with the Veneto equal to an amount of 0.9;
- Veneto has a link with the Marche for a value of 0.98;
- The Marche have a link with Friuli-Venezia Giulia for a value of 0.9.

There is also a simplified structure that connects Puglia to Campania with a value of 1.0.

Machine learning and predictions with original data. Below is a prediction with Machine Learning algorithms compared according to their ability to maximize R^2 and minimize the following statistical errors or "Mean Absolute Error", "Mean Squared Error", "Root Mean Squared Error ". The algorithms were trained with 70% of the data while the remaining 30% was used for the actual prediction. It therefore derives the following order of the algorithms or:

- Tree regression ensemble with a payoff value of 4;
- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 8;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 12;
- Ann-artificial neural network with a payoff value of 16;
- Gradient Boosted Trees with a payoff value of 20;
- PNN-Probabilistic neural Network with a payoff value of 24;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 28;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value of 32.

Therefore by applying the Tree Ensemble Regression it is possible to predict the following trend of excess weight in the Italian regions:

- Abruzzo with an increased variation from an amount of 46.50 up to a value of 48.78 units or equal to an amount of 2.28 units equal to a value of 4.91%;
- Basilicata with an increased variation from an amount of 50.00 units up to a value of 50.51 units or equal to a value of 0.51 units or equal to a variation of 1.02%;
- Calabria with an increased variation from an amount of 48.40 units up to a value of 48.49 units or a variation of 0.09 units equal to an amount of 0.18%;

- Campania with a diminutive variation from an amount of 55.30 units up to a value of 49.20 units or equal to a variation of -6.10 units equal to an amount of -11.03%;
- Emilia Romagna with a diminutive variation from an amount of 45.40 units up to a value of 43.94 units or equal to a variation of -1.46 units equal to a value of -3.21%;
- Friuli Venezia Giulia with a diminutive variation from an amount of 44.30 units up to a value of 43.13 units or equal to a variation of -1.18 units equal to a value of -2.65%;
- Lazio with a variation from an amount of 43.00 units up to a value of 43.55 units or equal to a variation of 0.55 units equal to an amount of 1.28%;
- Liguria with a diminutive variation from an amount of 42.60 units up to a value of 42.42 units or equal to a variation of -0.19 units equal to an amount of -0.43%;
- Lombardy with a diminutive variation from an amount of 43.30 units up to a value of 42.15 units or equal to a variation of -1.15 units equal to a value of -2.65%;
- Marche with an increased variation from an amount of 43.50 units up to a value of 44.02 units or equal to a variation of 0.52 units equal to an amount of 1.20%;
- Molise with a diminutive variation from an amount of 49.30 units up to a value of 48.14 units or equal to a variation of -1.16 units equal to an amount of -2.34%;
- Piedmont with an increased variation from an amount of 41.90 units up to a value of 42.12 units or equal to a variation of 0.22 units equal to an amount of 0.52%;
- Puglia with an increased variation from a value of 48.00 units up to a value of 50.34 units or equal to a variation of 2.34 units equal to a variation of 4.88%;
- Sardinia with an increased variation from an amount of 42.50 units up to a value of 42.77 units or equal to a variation of 0.27 units equal to an amount of 0.63%;
- Sicily with a diminutive variation from an amount of 51.20 units up to a value of 48.75 units or equal to a variation of -2.45 units equal to a variation of -4.79%;
- Tuscany with an increased variation from an amount of 40.40 units up to a value of 43.28 units or equal to a variation of 2.88 units equal to a variation of 7.13%;
- Trentino Alto Adige with a variation from an amount of 40.70 units up to a value of 42.29 units or equal to a value of 1.59 units equal to an amount of 3.90%;
- Umbria with an increased variation from an amount of 43.90 units up to a value of 44.99 units or equal to a variation of 1.09 units equal to an amount of 2.48%;
- Valle d'Aosta with a diminutive variation from an amount of 43.50 units up to a value of 42.31 units or equal to a variation -1.19 units equal to an amount of -2.73%;
- Veneto with a variation of 43.90 units up to a value of 42.86 units equal to a variation of -1.04 units equal to a value of -2.37%.

Average with a diminutive variation from an amount of 45.38 units up to a value of 45.20 units or equal to a variation of -0.18 units equal to a variation of -0.39%. The prediction that has been created thus is added to the historical series. In this way, a new data set of "increased" data is determined. Using this new dataset, the algorithms for the prediction of access to weight in the Italian regions were confronted again. The algorithms system is indicated below or:

- Random Forest Regression with a 4 Payoff value;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 8;
- PNN-Probabilistic neural Network with a value of the payoff equal to 12;
- Tree regression ensemble with a payoff value of 16;
- Ann-artificial neural network with a payoff value of 20;
- Gradient Boosted Tree with a payoff value of 24;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value of 28;

- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 32.
- It follows therefore that by applying the Random Forest Regression algorithm it is possible to predict the following variations of excess weight in the Italian regions:
- Campania with a value of the augmentative prediction from an amount of 49.20 units up to a value of 50.08 units or equal to an amount of 0.88 units equal to a value of 1.79%;
- Lombardy with an increased variation from an amount of 42.15 units up to a value of 42.48 units or equal to a value of 0.33 units equal to a value of 0.78%;
- Marche with an increased variation from an amount of 44.02 units up to a value of 43.45 units or equal to a variation of -0.57 units equal to a value of -1.29%;
- Molise with an increased variation from an amount of 48.14 units up to a value of 49.15 units or equal to a value of 1.00 units equal to a variation of 2.08%;
- Piedmont with an increased variation from an amount of 42.12 units up to a value of 42.39 units or equal to a variation of 0.27 units equal to an amount of 0.63%;
- Sardinia with a variation of 42.77 units up to a value of 42.91 units or equal to a variation of 0.14 units equal to an amount of 0.34%.

Finally, the average value is predicted growing from an amount of 44.73 units up to a value of 45.08 units or equal to a variation of 0.34 units equal to a value of 0.76%.

Conclusions. In summary, the value of excess weight had a reductive trend in the center-Italy and southern Italy and a growth in northern Italy between 2005 and 2020. However, considering Italy there was one growth of 1.1 units of excess weight. In addition, clusterization shows that the value of excess weight divides the country into two areas: the center-north with low values, and the South with significantly higher values. Since excess weight is associated with a set of pathologies such as diabetes and hypertension that are very expensive on an individual and social level, then it is possible that in the future the southern health systems, which are widely undersized compared to those of the North, they are called to further interventions on the population to reduce the cost of health care through the change in living habits.

Declarations

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Appendix

Eccesso di peso nelle Regioni Italiane nel 2020		
Rank	Regione	2020
1	<i>Campania</i>	★ 55,3
2	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 51,2
3	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 50
4	<i>Molise</i>	★ 49,3
5	<i>Calabria</i>	★ 48,4
6	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 48
7	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 46,5
8	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 45,4
9	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	☆ 44,3
10	<i>Veneto</i>	☆ 43,9
10	<i>Umbria</i>	☆ 43,9
11	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	☆ 43,5
11	<i>Marche</i>	☆ 43,5
12	<i>Lombardia</i>	☆ 43,3
13	<i>Lazio</i>	☆ 43
14	<i>Liguria</i>	☆ 42,6
15	<i>Sardegna</i>	☆ 42,5
16	<i>Piemonte</i>	☆ 41,9
17	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	☆ 40,7
18	<i>Toscana</i>	☆ 40,4

Eccesso di peso nelle Regioni Italiane nel 2020

Variazione dell'Eccesso di Peso tra il 2005 ed il 2020

Rank	Regione	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	★ 6,8	★ 18,53
2	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ 5	★ 13,05
3	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ 3,2	★ 8,27
4	<i>Liguria</i>	★ 2,6	★ 6,50
5	<i>Campania</i>	★ 2,7	★ 5,13
6	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 1,6	★ 3,23
7	<i>Umbria</i>	★ 0,7	★ 1,62
8	<i>Veneto</i>	★ 0,5	★ 1,15
9	<i>Molise</i>	★ 0,5	★ 1,02
10	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 0,3	★ 0,67
11	<i>Marche</i>	★ -0,5	★ -1,14
12	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ -0,9	★ -2,07
13	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ -1,1	★ -2,42
14	<i>Lazio</i>	★ -1,8	★ -4,02
15	<i>Calabria</i>	★ -2,2	★ -4,35
16	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ -2,7	★ -5,12
17	<i>Toscana</i>	★ -2,7	★ -6,26
18	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	★ -2,8	★ -6,44
19	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ -4,4	★ -8,64
20	<i>Puglia</i>	★ -5	★ -9,43

Variazione Assoluta dell'Eccesso di Peso tra il 2005 ed il 2020.

Variazione Percentuale dell'Eccesso di Peso tra il 2005 ed il 2020.

Variazioni dell'Eccesso di Peso

<i>Macro-Regione</i>	2005	2020	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Nord</i>	40,90	43,40	2,50	6,11
<i>Centro</i>	43,90	42,20	-1,70	-3,87
<i>Mezzogiorno</i>	50,80	50,40	-0,40	-0,79
<i>Italia</i>	45,00	45,50	0,50	1,11

Regione	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Piemonte	38,7	40,4	40,1	40,7	39,8	41,1	40,6	42	39,3	39,5	39,4	39,1	40,2	42,1	41,2	41,9
Valle d'Aosta/Vallee d'Aoste	36,7	41	42,4	42,6	43,2	43,7	41,3	41,2	41,8	39,3	39,9	42,8	40,6	42,1	40,3	43,5
Liguria	40	38,4	40,5	38,6	38	38,5	40,5	36,7	38,1	41,4	41,1	41,6	38,3	42,4	41,4	42,6
Lombardia	38,3	39,9	40,1	42,4	43,1	41	41,1	42	40,4	42,1	39,3	41,7	42,1	40	40,8	43,3
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	43,5	40,3	40,9	40,8	41	40,3	39,8	40,5	41,2	39,1	38,2	38,1	39,4	39,7	38,1	40,7
Veneto	43,4	45,2	43,7	42,5	45	44,4	44	44,1	43,9	44,1	43,2	44	42,2	43,7	42,7	43,9
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	45,4	43,9	42,4	42,4	45,7	46,3	47,8	43,8	44	43,2	39,8	43,9	44,7	42,9	41,2	44,3
Emilia-Romagna	45,1	45,4	45,2	45,3	46	45,1	46,8	43,2	43,9	46,6	43,3	44,8	47,1	44,5	47,1	45,4
Toscana	43,1	42,1	42,4	43,2	42,3	41,8	41,9	43,2	43,2	42,7	43,5	43,5	41,5	41,3	42	40,4
Umbria	43,2	45,6	45,2	46,9	46,7	47,7	48	48,6	44,6	45,4	42,9	46,2	43,1	46,6	43,5	43,9
Marche	44	45,1	43,8	44,1	45,2	45,1	46,7	43,5	43,4	46,2	39,3	44,5	43,4	44,2	43,9	43,5
Lazio	44,8	44,3	44,5	43,1	45,8	45,7	43,2	42,8	44,8	42	44,7	40,9	41,8	44	44,9	43
Abruzzo	50,9	49,8	49,3	47,8	49,2	48,1	47,4	50,9	46,8	49,3	47,8	50,2	47,1	48,8	44,8	46,5
Molise	48,8	49,8	51,5	51,8	50,8	52,2	49,5	52	50,6	51,9	51,1	50,6	46,5	50,7	50,9	49,3
Campania	52,6	52,8	53,9	52,8	53	53,5	52,1	53,1	52,8	53,4	51,6	51,8	51,3	51,7	51,2	55,3
Puglia	53	51,1	51,8	51,7	50,9	51,6	53,7	52	51,1	51,1	50,1	49,6	50,6	49,7	51	48
Basilicata	52,7	52,7	51,2	52,9	49,1	54,4	48,9	51,9	52,8	50,5	49	51,3	52,2	50,7	51,1	50
Calabria	50,6	49,5	48,8	49,2	52,1	50,9	49	48,1	48,3	51,4	48	50,4	47,9	50,1	50,7	48,4
Sicilia	49,6	50,7	52,9	49,3	50,5	48,9	48,7	49,7	50,2	49,9	47,3	48,7	51,4	50,6	49,6	51,2
Sardegna	43,4	40,1	43,8	43,2	45,1	45,5	43,1	42,2	42,2	41,5	42,1	42,7	40,6	38,2	39,7	42,5

Ranking degli algoritmi con i dati aumentati

Algoritmo	R ²	mean absolute error	mean squared error	root mean squared error	Totale
<i>Random Forest Regression</i>	1	1	1	1	4
<i>Simple Regression Tree</i>	2	2	2	2	8
<i>PNN</i>	3	3	3	3	12
<i>Tree Ensemble Regression</i>	4	4	4	4	16
<i>ANN</i>	5	5	5	5	20
<i>Gradient Boosted Tree</i>	6	6	6	6	24
<i>Polynomial Regression</i>	7	7	7	7	28
<i>Linear Regression</i>	8	8	8	8	32

Predizione con Dati Aumentati				
Regione	Predizione	Predizione(predizione)	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Campania</i>	49,20	50,08	0,88	1,79
<i>Lombardia</i>	42,15	42,48	0,33	0,78
<i>Marche</i>	44,02	43,45	-0,57	-1,29
<i>Molise</i>	48,14	49,15	1,00	2,08
<i>Piemonte</i>	42,12	42,39	0,27	0,63
<i>Sardegna</i>	42,77	42,91	0,14	0,34
<i>Media</i>	44,73	45,08	0,34	0,76

Ranking degli Algoritmi per Efficienza Predittiva					
Algoritmo	R^2	mean absolute error	mean squared error	root mean squared error	Totale
<i>Tree Ensemble Regression</i>	1	1	1	1	4
<i>Random Forest Regression</i>	2	2	2	2	8
<i>Simple Regression Tree</i>	3	3	3	3	12
<i>ANN</i>	4	4	4	4	16
<i>Gradient Boosted Trees</i>	5	5	5	5	20
<i>PNN</i>	6	6	6	6	24
<i>Linear Regression</i>	7	7	7	7	28
<i>Polynomial Regression</i>	8	8	8	8	32

Predizione con Dati Originali									
Regione	2020	Predizione	Var Ass	Var Per	Regione	2020	Predizione	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Abruzzo</i>	46,50	48,78	2,28	4,91	<i>Molise</i>	49,30	48,14	-1,16	-2,34
<i>Basilicata</i>	50,00	50,51	0,51	1,02	<i>Piemonte</i>	41,90	42,12	0,22	0,53
<i>Calabria</i>	48,40	48,49	0,09	0,18	<i>Puglia</i>	48,00	50,34	2,34	4,88
<i>Campania</i>	55,30	49,20	-6,10	-11,03	<i>Sardegna</i>	42,50	42,77	0,27	0,63
<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	45,40	43,94	-1,46	-3,21	<i>Sicilia</i>	51,20	48,75	-2,45	-4,79
<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	44,30	43,13	-1,18	-2,65	<i>Toscana</i>	40,40	43,28	2,88	7,13
<i>Lazio</i>	43,00	43,55	0,55	1,28	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	40,70	42,29	1,59	3,90
<i>Liguria</i>	42,60	42,42	-0,19	-0,43	<i>Umbria</i>	43,90	44,99	1,09	2,48
<i>Lombardia</i>	43,30	42,15	-1,15	-2,65	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	43,50	42,31	-1,19	-2,73
<i>Marche</i>	43,50	44,02	0,52	1,20	<i>Veneto</i>	43,90	42,86	-1,04	-2,37

	2020	Regione	Cluster	Silhouette
13	46.5	Abruzzo	C1	0.649391
17	50.0	Basilicata	C1	0.700461
18	48.4	Calabria	C1	0.689677
15	55.3	Campania	C1	0.701115
8	45.4	Emilia-Romagna	C2	0.602431
7	44.3	Friuli-Venezia G...	C2	0.664106
12	43.0	Lazio	C2	0.664812
3	42.6	Liguria	C2	0.678194
4	43.3	Lombardia	C2	0.692839
11	43.5	Marche	C2	0.659702
14	49.3	Molise	C1	0.700282
1	41.9	Piemonte	C2	0.689565
16	48.0	Puglia	C1	0.704001
20	42.5	Sardegna	C2	0.685488
19	51.2	Sicilia	C1	0.692741
9	40.4	Toscana	C2	0.690134
5	40.7	Trentino-Alto A...	C2	0.685268
10	43.9	Umbria	C2	0.576071
2	43.5	Valle d'Aosta/V...	C2	0.69093
6	43.9	Veneto	C2	0.676391

